

	Reporting Item	Page Number
Title and abstract		
Title	#1a Indicate the study's design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract	NA
Abstract	#1b Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found	1
Introduction		
Background / rationale	#2 Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	3
Objectives	#3 State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses	3
Methods		
Study design	#4 Present key elements of study design early in the paper	3,4
Setting	#5 Describe the setting, locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment, exposure, follow-up, and data collection	3,4
Eligibility criteria	#6a Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants.	4
	#7 Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors, potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable	4
Data sources / measurement	#8 For each variable of interest give sources of data and details of methods of assessment (measurement). Describe comparability of assessment methods if there is more than one group. Give information separately for for exposed and unexposed groups if applicable.	4
Bias	#9 Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	NA
Study size	#10 Explain how the study size was arrived at	NA

Quantitative variables	#11	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses. If applicable, describe which groupings were chosen, and why	4
Statistical methods	#12a	Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding	4
Statistical methods	#12b	Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions	NA
Statistical methods	#12c	Explain how missing data were addressed	4
Statistical methods	#12d	If applicable, describe analytical methods taking account of sampling strategy	NA
Statistical methods	#12e	Describe any sensitivity analyses	NA
Results			
Participants	#13a	Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study—eg numbers potentially eligible, examined for eligibility, confirmed eligible, included in the study, completing follow-up, and analysed. Give information separately for exposed and unexposed groups if applicable.	5
Participants	#13b	Give reasons for non-participation at each stage	NA
Participants	#13c	Consider use of a flow diagram	NA
Descriptive data	#14a	Give characteristics of study participants (eg demographic, clinical, social) and information on exposures and potential confounders. Give information separately for exposed and unexposed groups if applicable.	5,6
Descriptive data	#14b	Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable of interest	9
Outcome data	#15	Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures. Give information separately for exposed and unexposed groups if applicable.	NA
Main results	#16a	Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision (eg, 95% confidence	9

interval). Make clear which confounders were adjusted for and why they were included

Main results	#16b	Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorized	5
Main results	#16c	If relevant, consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk for a meaningful time period	NA
Other analyses	#17	Report other analyses done—e.g., analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	NA
Discussion			
Key results	#18	Summarise key results with reference to study objectives	9,10,11
Limitations	#19	Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision. Discuss both direction and magnitude of any potential bias.	11
Interpretation	#20	Give a cautious overall interpretation considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence.	10,11
Generalisability	#21	Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	11
Other Information			
Funding	#22	Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study and, if applicable, for the original study on which the present article is based	12

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